

LIFE, WORKS AND STORIES OF PRIMKUL KADIROV.

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Writer, translator, publicist, scholar of literature, one of the great representatives of Uzbek prose, Pirmkul Kadirov was born on October 25, 1928 in the village of Kengkol at the foot of the mountain range of Turkestan. He is originally from the Barlos people of Uzbek, and in the years after the war, he worked on a collective farm, road construction, and then at the Bekobod metallurgical plant. In 1951, he graduated from the Faculty of Oriental Studies of the Central Asian State University and entered the graduate school of the Institute of Literature named after M. Gorky in Moscow. He defended his candidate's thesis on the topic "Post-war creativity of Abdullah Qahhor". In 1954-1963, he worked as a consultant on Uzbek literature under the Union of Writers of the former Union, a senior researcher at the Institute of Language and Literature of the RFA (1963-1983), and the chairman of the State Prize Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of literature, art and architecture (1989-1994). Adib The prelude to his work - the story "Students" (1951) was published during his student years and illuminates the life of the student of science and their inner world. After that, the stories "Jon Shirin", "Kaif", "Olov", the stories "Kadrim" (1961), "Erk" (1968), "Meros" (1974), the legendary stories "Salvation", "Bahillar va Batirlar" (1980), "Adventures of Akram" (1974), "Yaira is going to enter the institute" (1970) and collections of short stories and short stories were published one after another. Kadyrov penned in the novel genre and wrote the novels "Three Roots" (1958), "Olmos Kamar" (1976). Adib made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek historical novels with the novels "Starry Nights" (1979) and then "Avlodlar Dovani" (1989). Three volumes of selected works of the writer (1977-1978) were published in Gafur Ghulom's Adabiyot va sanat publishing house. Pirmkul Kadirov As a literary scholar, he created the pamphlets "Til va el" (1972), "People's language and realistic prose" (1973), "Til va dil" (2005). He wrote the chapters "Language of Literary Work" and "Literary Process" for the two-volume "Literary Theory".

On the basis of the short story "Kadrim" about the workers of Zangori Olov, the feature film "Sening izlaring" (director R. Botyrov), the novel "Starry Nights" and the story "Jon Shirin" were shot. The play "Babur" (directed by B. Yoldoshev) has

been staged in the Uzbek National Academic Drama Theater for many years, and the play "Insof" has been staged in regional drama theaters. Adib presented his historical novel "Mother's Falcon's Call" (1997) to readers. In 2001, his book "Eyes of the Heart" (fables, thoughts, memories) was published. The study "The figure of Amir Temur" (2007) took an important place in the unbiased study of our history. As a translator, Kadyrov translated the stories and novels of L. Tolstoy's "Cossacks", K. Fedin's "First Joys", P. Tolis' "Iz", Kh. Deryaev's "Kismat" into our native language. His works were published in Russian, Ukrainian, Hindi, Urdu, Turkish, Uyghur, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkmen languages. In 1981, Pirimkul Kadyrov was awarded the State Prize of the Republic for the novel "Starry Nights". He was a deputy of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1997-2000), the chairman of the science, culture and education committee of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1991-1995).), was awarded the order "For Meritorious Services" (2006). My two sisters remained loyal to their husbands, who died defending the Motherland during the war, and never remarried. One of them raised two boys and one of three children without a father. There are such mothers in every village and city. I would like to express my utmost respect to all of them through this story.

There was a knock at the gate at two in the morning. Lying on the porch, Alisher fell fast asleep and did not wake up quickly. After knocking harder on the gate, the door of the inner house opened with a creak, and sister Iqbal went out to the porch. Alisher just woke up and got up. While he was getting dressed in the dark, he said to the gate:

"Now!" - he said.

Sister Iqbal tried to suppress an inner tremor:

"Look quickly, isn't it your father?" he said. Alisher asked back in a sleepy voice:

- Who do you say?

- Your father!

Alisher was surprised:

"You're not interested, honey!" - he said, quickly got off the porch and went to the gatehouse.

It has been more than thirty years since Alisher's father, Umarjon, went missing in the war.

The thing that sister Iqbal is most afraid of is "laughter". Going missing seems longer than that anyway. She waits for her husband to come in suddenly, and when there is a knock at the gate at night, her heart breaks and she says to the children, "Aren't they your fathers?" he won't say it.

As a child, Alisher, like his bear, always kept his eye on his father's path. But as he grew older, he began to doubt whether his father was alive. If he was alive, wouldn't he have been looking for his beloved wife and children like flowers for thirty years?! Or even if he was on the other side of the world, wouldn't he send a message or a letter?!

- What did not happen in this war! Sister Iqbal said to her son. - If your father was captured while wounded, were they taken to foreign countries? If something bad happened to him, did he keep silent on purpose, saying, "My children will not be blamed"? If one day he does a good deed that justifies himself, will the way be opened and he will come?

These assumptions aroused complex and complicated thoughts in Alisher. When Alisher got tired of these complications, he wanted to prove that his father had died on the battlefield. He heard that there is a special office in Moscow that deals with the search for missing fighters, so he wrote several letters there. He sent copies of his father's last photos, letters, and addresses. The delay went on and on and on and lasted for several years. Finally, last autumn, in the reply from Moscow, it was said that most of the soldiers of the rifle company in which Umarjon Rahimov served were killed in the heavy battles for the city of Ternopil in Western Ukraine. It was assumed that Umarjon Rahimov was also killed among them, but no concrete documents were found. Because after the liberation of Ternopil once, due to the treachery of the banders, the secret printer, the city temporarily fell into the hands of the enemy, and many documents were lost.

If there are no documents, maybe there are living people? Alisher now wrote letters with this question to Ternopil city authorities, even to youth organizations - detachments of young Iztopars. No result. In one of the replies, it was said that it was difficult to solve this complicated problem by letter, and that someone who knows the signs of missing warriors could come and find something.

Who goes? Sister Iqbal worked at the factory for thirty years and recently retired. But his health is bad. He missed his diabetes medication. High blood pressure. In this situation, if she suddenly finds her husband's grave, won't she lose her last attachment and end her life?

"I will go myself," Alisher said. His sister Mahfuza did not agree to this:

"You don't remember my father." You were a baby. What do you say when people ask for a sign! I saw my father. I'll go...

It has been eight days since Mahfuza left. That's why Alisher's thoughts immediately went to his sister when there was a knock at the gate.

"Zaporojets" was busy running the corridor of the gatehouse. Alisher went to the left side of the car and found the button of the electric light in the dark. After the light came on in the corridor, an old man from outside said:

— Telegram! - was heard a rasping sound.

Alisher opened one of the gates and signed the receipt of the telegram in the light of the lamp.

In the meantime, Sister Iqbal put her headscarf on her head and came down from the porch to the gatehouse.

Alisher put the folded telegram in the light of the lamp and impatiently opened it.

"I found what I was looking for. I will take an evening flight from Kiev. Meet at three o'clock Tashkent time. Mahfuza".

The word "found" made Alisher gasp. He turned to his bear, his eyes shining.

"My sister!" he said.

- What did he say? Did you find your father's tree?

"Looks like he found it!"

"Oh my god!" Where did they go? Why didn't they come until now?!

Sister Iqbal was speaking believing that her husband was found alive. Alisher suddenly felt worried. Maybe Mahfuza found the grave of his father. The brothers had no doubt that their father had died. After all, could a living person sit quietly in Ternopil for so many years? But the bear didn't think about it. If he earnestly believes that he is "found alive" and then it turns out to be the opposite, his illness will get worse.

"Oijan, don't believe it right away!"

"Yes, why now?"

"Just think about it... Let my sister come, she will tell the truth."

"When are you coming?"

- At three in the morning. What time is it now?... Oh, it's been forty minutes!... I have to go out soon!

Alisher's young wife also woke up and hurriedly dressed. "Zaporojets" roared and walked out of the gate with his back to the street. Sister Iqbal followed her daughter-in-law to the airport with her son and returned to the porch.

Three children, younger than each other, are cooking and sleeping on the porch. A crescent moon floats in the sky.

Sister Iqbal entered the inner house where she lived and went to the old chest on the net. He pulled down the velvet blankets that were folded over the chest. Then he took the key hanging from the nail on the shelf and put it in the lock of the chest.

The box creaked open with a soft sound, and the smell of peppermint came from inside. Brother Umarjon loved pepper beads. Sometimes he put a couple of pieces of it in his mouth and rolled them between his teeth, and when he spoke, his breath smelled like pepper beads. Remembering this, sister Iqbal kept his clothes and letters together with pepper beads.

Here is the yellow Jujun shirt and pants that brother Umarjon wore thirty years ago, a shirt with Iraqi embroidery on the collar and sleeves, chrome boots... Brother Umarjon wrote in his letters from the front: "It's not easy for you to feed two young children, you don't spare the things in the house, if necessary, sell my clothes and buy food, if we survive, we will find something, take care of yourself and the children!" was appointed as Even when Iqbal sold her dowry and jewelry, she kept all her husband's clothes, aired them once or twice a year and put them back on.

By the time Alisher became a big boy, jujube jackets and shirts with embroidered collars were out of fashion. Alisher, who is now an architect and draws projects, did not even wear his father's chrome boots. Sorry, why don't modern intellectuals wear boots? Brother Umarjon was also a teacher. He taught botany at school, but he wore boots.

Well, even if the clothes in the chest are out of the picture, if brother Umarjon comes, sister Iqbal will definitely wear them to her husband. There is also a beautiful flute in the chest. The elegant silver rings of this flute, made of Kashgar hornet, are extremely suitable. The silver dome at one end of the flute is decorated with a small blue turquoise.

Brother Umarjon used to play on this flute sometimes "Navo", sometimes "Dugoh", sometimes strange tunes that sister Iqbal did not know. Then the whole being would be filled with pleasure and melt away. Even now, it was as if the flute suddenly appeared, and her husband, who was playing it, appeared in front of sister Iqbal's eyes. When Umarjon put his lips to the hole of the flute, opened his mouth and played a tune, the rays of light reflected in his white teeth twinkled unknowingly in the silver rings. Now it seems that this shine has reappeared in the pipe. The tunes played by brother Umarjon on the flute seemed to be heard from the heart of sister Iqbal. In his heart, there were also elegant, beautiful strings similar to the curtains of a flute, which only brother Umarjon could play.

Sister Iqbal has not given this flute to anyone since her husband went to war. Nai has been silent for thirty-two years. The feeling of love in the heart of sister Iqbal is still waiting for brother Umarjan...

Umarjon was a twenty-three-year-old boy when he wore these clothes and played the flute. Sister Iqbal was a bride in her twenties.

Those beautiful moments are still alive in the folds of these clothes, mixed with the smell of pepper beads, turning into shimmering shuls on the surface of the flute. True, sister Iqbal is now retired and has a grandchild. But in his heart is the right of thirty-two years of hijran. She wants to go back to her twenties even for a moment, she wants to go through her thirties and forties again with her beloved husband.

Only for this wish to come true, brother Umarjon must return. If only Zora would come in now with her children!

Mahfuza said in a telegram that he "found it". Would he say that if he didn't find his father?

The feeling that had been living in the heart of sister Iqbal for so many years turned into trust. He put the electric iron on. Then brother Umarjon took out the clothes from the chest and started ironing. At dawn, the engine of "Zaporojets" was heard on the street. Sister Iqbal hastily went out to the yard, and Mahfuza entered through the gate. Mother and child hugged each other. Sister Iqbal pressed her face to her daughter's face. Then he felt that Mahfuza's face was wet with tears, and his heart sank.

"How did you get there?" Did you find your father or not?!

- The trees were found, dear...

Alisher drove his car into the gatehouse and got out of it.

"Come on, let's go into the house and talk," he said.

His appearance was also gloomy. The events that his sister had told him since he got off the plane, the details of the brutal war thirty years ago, had horrified him...

On the night when the city of Ternopol was captured by the Nazis for the second time with the help of banders, brother Umarjon took refuge in a six-room house with his unit and fought until his last breath. He let the women and children of the house down through the back window and abducted them. Otherwise, they will die without leaving one. Because the fascists overthrew the house where the Umarjon brothers were hiding with a heavy tank...

When Ternopil was liberated from the enemy for the second time, the bodies of the soldiers who died under the ruins were dug up and buried in the grave of the brothers, but many of them could not be recognized, their names were not revealed...

Only one of the children, whom Umarjon saved by escaping from the back window, remembers him well. When they stayed together in this house for some time, brother Umarjon said that he was from Uzbekistan, that he had a son and a daughter in Tashkent, and the boy remembered this. Now this boy is a forty-year-old teacher. A teacher working at this school heard that the Iztopars from Ternopil took Alisher's letter in Tashkent and searched for documents related to his father.

Mahfuza, who came from Koramaghiz, had thin eyebrows and slanted eyes, was very similar to his father. After he goes looking for his father, the teacher remembers brother Umarjon at first sight. Even the fact that the fighters called him "Umar" now comes to mind. One of the women who escaped from the window and was saved by brother Umarjon lives in this city. Then they will all go to the military commissariat and testify about how Umarjon Rahimov died, what courage he showed before his death and where he was buried. Brother Umarjon was buried in the fraternal grave of eighty people, which was placed in the center of the city - in a magnificent marble monument. But his name was not among the names written on the marble, as his identity and how he died have not yet been determined. Mahfuza met with the city organizations and returned with his father's name written on the marble monument.

He wrote treatises on the scientific-theoretical issues of the Uzbek language and literature ("Til and language", 1972 and others) and the chapters "Language of a literary work" and "Literary process" for the 2-volume "Theory of Literature".

Based on the short story "Kadrim", the feature film "Singing Izlaring", the novel "Starry Nights" and the story "Sweet Soul" were filmed. Pirimkul Kadirov died on December 21, 2010 in Tashkent.

Honored Culture Worker of Uzbekistan (1978). Laureate of the State Prize of Uzbekistan (1981). People's writer of Uzbekistan (1988). He was awarded the "Honor of the Country" (1998), "Shuhrat" medal (1994), "For Great Services" (2006) orders.

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